

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Singhateh****FIRST NAME: Fatoumatta****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2013 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- In the WHO style guide, which rule is use to convey distinction in sense when the first part of the compound does not modify the meaning of the second part?**
 - Parentheses
 - Word breaks
 - Semi colon.
 - Em rule.¹**

- Which of the following three currency codes are for WHO internal use only and should not appear in publications?**
 - CHF, GBP, USD.²**

¹ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 22.

² Ibid, 7.

- USD, CFA, GBP.
- GBP, GMB, USD.
- CHF, USD, CHF.

3. **All the following are right about long quotations except?**

- They look like your own research.**³
- They will take no quotation mark.
- They should be indented or use EUCLID template use the quote style.
- They are over four lines long.

4. **What should I do when an article does not sound, right?**

- Let your ear be your guide.
- Put a before a consonant and an before a vowel.
- Put “a” before a consonant sound and “an” before a vowel sound.**⁴
- All of the above are correct to be used.

5. **A paper which reduced multiple cause to one or few this act by the writer is referred to as?**

- Oversimplification.**⁵

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 7.

⁴ Ibid, 21.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 9.

- Superficiality
 - Anthropomorphism
 - Subjectivity
6. **When citing a book with four authors according to Harvard style citing and referencing, which of the following Latin abbreviation is correct to use rather than list all the authors?**
- Et al.**⁶
 - Verse vasa.
 - Ibid.
 - Al et.
7. **Which of the following traits listed below identify the main features of the best write-up?**
- Superficiality and the use of subjectivity.
 - Extensive details, citation, and referencing.
 - Stimulating ideas, logical organization, and engaging voice.**⁷
 - Introduction, discussion, and conclusions.
8. **Which of the following step of writing lays the solid foundation of an essay?**

⁶ Ibid, 60.

⁷ Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000. A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington, Massachusetts:Great Source Publishing Group, 1999), 20.

Prewriting.⁸

Gathering details.

Drafting.

Group Advising.

9. **Among the listed forms of research questions, which one is commonly used in academic work?**

Conceptual questions.⁹

Practical questions.

Applied questions.

Critical questions.

10. **Researchers put more faith in which type of arguments?**

Arguments based on evidence.¹⁰

Paradoxical arguments.

Arguments based on warrants.

Critical arguments.

⁸ Ibid, 45.

⁹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16.

¹⁰ Ibid, 41.

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